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Teaching language in chunks: the impact of collocations and fixed expressions on ESL learners' fluency

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***Abstract.** The chunk-based teaching approach is described in the literature as a pedagogical technique that enables complex texts to be broken down into discrete units, or “chunks” (lexical phrases, set expressions, and fixed phrases), thereby reducing cognitive overload. Collocations, idiomatic expressions, and other lexical chunks carry important cultural and pragmatic information, enabling learners to communicate appropriately and naturally in diverse contexts. In addition, mastering these pre-fabricated language units enhances both spoken and written proficiency while increasing learner motivation by allowing immediate, comprehensible, and successful language use. This study investigates the effectiveness of chunk-based instruction, focusing on collocations and fixed expressions, in enhancing language production, communicative competence, and oral fluency among ESL engineering students from the teachers’ perspectives. Quantitative data were collected through questionnaires that assessed attitudes, beliefs, and perceived fluency gains. The findings reveal a consensus among respondents, ESL teachers, on the effectiveness of chunk-based teaching, with positive attitudes expressed towards its benefits for students’ speaking fluency, confidence, and overall communicative ability. Although acknowledging the inherent challenges of mastering collocations and idioms, participants recognized the potential of chunk-based instruction to enhance learners’ linguistic performance. Thus, it provides empirical evidence for the effectiveness of integrating pre-fabricated language chunks into the ESL curriculum. Further research should investigate the longitudinal effects of systematic chunk instruction on language production and fluency development. Practical recommendations for curriculum design, teacher training, and instructional practices are needed to optimize the implementation of chunk-based learning in ESL contexts.*

Key words: chunk-based instruction; lexical chunks; collocations; fixed expressions; formulaic language; ESL fluency; communicative competence; speaking fluency; naturalness of learner output.

Навчання мови через лексичні фрагменти: вплив словосполучень та усталених виразів на плинність мовлення студентів, що вивчають англійську як другу мову

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Анотація. Підхід до навчання на основі лексичних фрагментів (*chunk-based teaching*) у сучасній лінгводидактиці розглядається як ефективна педагогічна методика, що передбачає опрацювання мови через готові багатослівні одиниці (лексичні фрази, словосполучення, сталі та фіксовані вирази), сприяючи зменшенню когнітивного навантаження під час мовленнєвої обробки. Лексичні фрагменти акумулюють важливу культурну та прагматичну інформацію, забезпечуючи природність і доречність мовлення в різних комунікативних ситуаціях. Оволодіння такими одиницями позитивно впливає на розвиток усного й писемного мовлення, а також підвищує мотивацію студентів завдяки можливості швидкого та успішного використання мови. У статті досліджується ефективність навчання, орієнтованого на *chunk-based* підхід (з акцентом на словосполучення та усталені вирази) у формуванні мовленнєвої продукції, комунікативної компетентності та плинності усного мовлення студентів інженерних спеціальностей, які вивчають англійську мову як другу. Кількісні дані було отримано шляхом анкетування викладачів англійської мови, спрямованого на виявлення їхніх ставлень, переконань і оцінок впливу цього підходу на розвиток мовленнєвої плинності студентів. Результати дослідження засвідчили загальний консенсус серед викладачів щодо ефективності навчання, заснованого на лексичних фрагментах. Респонденти відзначили його позитивний вплив на плинність усного мовлення, мовленнєву впевненість і загальний рівень комунікативної компетентності студентів. Незважаючи на наявні труднощі в оволодінні словосполученнями та ідіоматичними виразами, респонденти підкреслили значний потенціал цього підходу для підвищення якості мовленнєвої продукції. Отримані результати підтверджують доцільність інтеграції готових мовних одиниць у навчальні програми з англійської мови як другої та окреслюють перспективи подальших

досліджень, спрямованих на вивчення довгострокового впливу систематичного навчання лексичним фрагментам.

***Ключові слова:** навчання, засноване на лексичних фрагментах; лексичні фрагменти; словосполучення; усталені вирази; формульна мова; плинність мовлення; комунікативна компетенція; природність мовлення.*

Problem statement. The acquisition of fluency in a second language remains a central goal for English as a Second Language (ESL) learners. Traditional approaches to language instruction often prioritize the teaching of individual words and grammatical rules, potentially overlooking the importance of lexical chunks in achieving communicative competence.

Despite extensive theoretical and empirical support for the role of lexical chunks in developing fluency, little attention has been paid to how ESL teachers conceptualize and implement chunk-based instruction in everyday teaching practice. Collocations and formulaic sequences are often treated incidentally rather than systematically, and teachers may lack sufficient training, methodological guidance, or curricular support to integrate chunk-focused pedagogy consistently. As a result, a gap may exist between teachers' awareness of the benefits of lexical chunks and their actual classroom practices. This issue is particularly significant in higher education contexts, including ESL instruction for engineering students, where fluent and natural oral communication is essential. Therefore, investigating teachers' perceptions and instructional behaviors is necessary to inform pedagogical innovation and professional development.

Theoretical background. In order to understand how lexical chunks contribute to language fluency, it is important to review key theoretical perspectives on collocations and formulaic language.

It is generally accepted that J. R. Firth [1] was the pioneering scholar to investigate collocations. He stated that “collocations of a given word are statements of the habitual or customary places of that word order, but not in other contextual order and emphatically not in any grammatical order.

Sinclair [2] developed the idiom principle, which suggests that native speakers rely on prefabricated or semi-prefabricated chunks (collocations, fixed expressions, sentence frames) rather than building sentences word by word. This theory explains why collocations feel more natural to native speakers - they are cognitively stored in the mental lexicon as single units, which makes language processing faster and more efficient.

Newell [3] defines a chunk as a memory unit formed by combining established chunks.

Sun, W., & Park [4] define collocation as an inherent linguistic pattern in which words consistently appear together, forming interconnected units. They argue that this phenomenon is widespread across languages, and it is accurate to assert that collocations are an integral part of natural languages.

By mastering these pre-fabricated units, learners can enhance their ability to process and produce language more efficiently, thereby improving their overall fluency.

Celce-Murcia and Olshtain’s [5] view of collocation as chunks of language was closely connected to cognitive, functional, and pedagogical approaches to language use. In their framework, collocations are not simply frequent word combinations, but mentally stored lexical units that native speakers have internalized through repeated exposure. Because these combinations are stored as ready-made chunks, native speakers can access them rapidly and automatically, which facilitates both language production and comprehension.

Previous research. Loc Thi Bui [6 p. 99-109] reviewed the role of collocations in English language teaching and learning, emphasizing their centrality to language proficiency in both spoken and written communication. The article synthesizes previous research on collocations and highlights how these lexical combinations are often underestimated in EFL contexts, which can hinder learners' fluency and communicative competence. Bui argues that collocation acquisition is a complex challenge for non-native speakers and that more systematic attention to collocations in instruction and materials is needed to support learners' language development. The review concludes that collocations should be deliberately integrated into English curricula to improve learners' processing and production skills, reinforcing the pedagogical value of formulaic language in EFL teaching.

Albelihi et al. [7] in their study investigate the effects of explicit lexical-chunk instruction on the speaking fluency of Saudi EFL learners aged 13–17. Using materials from *English Collocations in Use* and *Common Idioms in English*, they found significant improvement in the experimental group, no meaningful change in the control group, and generally positive learner attitudes toward lexical-chunk training.

Abdurahmanova S. [8] also investigates the pedagogical impact of collocation instruction on EFL learners' speaking development, emphasizing the function of lexical chunks in real-time language production. The study provides evidence that systematic teaching of collocations facilitates oral fluency and accuracy by reducing cognitive processing demands during speech. The findings further indicate that enhanced collocational competence supports pragmatic appropriateness and fosters affective gains, including increased communicative confidence and reduced speaking anxiety. These results substantiate the role of collocation-focused instruction as a core component of effective speaking pedagogy and highlight its value for promoting natural and authentic oral communication in EFL contexts.

Lu et al. [9 p. 1-12] view lexical chunks as multi-word units with both lexical and grammatical properties, highlighting their frequent occurrence in spoken output and their cognitive representation as integral language units. They argue that chunk usage plays a significant role in pragmatic competence and spoken language performance and suggest that insufficient attention to chunks may limit learners' oral communication, calling for pedagogical practices that better support chunk use in speaking.

Savchenko et al. [10 p. 328-342] position the lexical approach as a method for teaching grammar through lexis, where grammatical structures are learned as lexical chunks and collocations rather than as abstract rules. They argue that this method - particularly through exercises like matching, substitution, and contextual pattern practice - enables military and law enforcement students to internalize grammar as reusable, automated units, leading to more accurate and fluent spoken production in professional settings.

Chioukh C. [11 p. 151-161] provides empirical evidence on any existing interplay between vocabulary level and collocational knowledge among Algerian EFL learners. The results demonstrated a moderately positive and statistically significant correlation between the participants' knowledge of collocations and their overall vocabulary proficiency. These outcomes underscore the necessity of more systematically integrating explicit collocation and vocabulary instruction into language curricula, both at the undergraduate and advanced levels, to enhance learners' linguistic performance and optimize language acquisition outcomes.

By situating L2 chunking within a unified, usage-based framework, the study by Serene Y. Wang, Morten H. Christiansen [12] contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of why nativelike fluency remains difficult to attain in a second language. Overall, the analysis reinforces the theoretical significance of chunk-based processing in L2 acquisition and supports the view that facilitating chunk formation is essential for

overcoming cognitive constraints on language learning and achieving more fluent and natural L2 performance.

Breslaw and Laufer [13] demonstrate that teaching L2 collocations through unrelated grouping combined with L1–L2 contrastive analysis effectively reduces cognitive interference and enhances retention. Their research suggests this approach helps learners process incongruent collocations as unified lexical chunks rather than translated word pairs. Consequently, learners achieve greater accuracy and fluency in both comprehension and productive use. The study validates a structured pedagogical method that strategically leverages cross-linguistic comparison to build durable collocational competence.

Duong and Nguyen [14 p. 275-287] examined students' and lecturers' perceptions of collocation use in EFL academic writing at a Vietnamese university. Their findings indicated strong agreement on the benefits of collocations for fluency and academic appropriateness, alongside persistent difficulties caused by limited lexical knowledge, negative L1 transfer, and insufficient instructional focus. The study highlights the importance of explicit collocation instruction, extensive reading, and sustained practice to support effective collocational use in academic writing.

Boonyarattanasoontern et al. [15 p. 98-129] find that an explicit, corpus-based collocation instruction significantly improves Thai EFL learners' collocation recognition and reduces errors in writing. Their research indicates that verb + noun collocations are the most problematic, with errors stemming primarily from L1 negative transfer and intralingual synonymy strategies. The findings validate a form-focused pedagogical framework that raises learners' awareness of collocational patterns, thereby enhancing both accuracy and naturalness in L2 written production.

Formulation of the objectives of the research. The research aims to determine the experiences of ESL teachers with the chunk-based teaching approach and to evaluate

its effectiveness in enhancing language production and developing communicative competence in ESL engineering students. Fluency and naturalness of learner output are treated as the main evaluative criteria.

The research objectives are as follows:

1. To examine English teachers' perspectives on the role of collocations and idioms in developing oral fluency and promoting more natural learner output.
2. To explore ESL teachers' readiness to engage in systematic collocation teaching as a means of improving vocabulary development.
3. To outline recommendations for English teachers on how to teach chunks more effectively.

Hypothesis. ESL teachers are aware of the importance and benefits of teaching collocations, but do not consistently integrate them into everyday classroom practice.

Methods. To achieve the goal of the research, a survey was designed. The study involved 30 English teachers at the National Technical University of Ukraine "Igor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute".

To obtain a comprehensive understanding of the research problem, a mixed-methods approach was employed, with quantitative analysis conducted through a 20-item questionnaire and complemented by qualitative analyses to provide contextual depth. The questionnaire was employed with items grouped into four thematic sections (A–D) assessing beliefs, practices, perceived impacts, and challenges/attitudes. The questionnaires utilized standard five-point Likert-type scales to measure agreement (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree) and frequency of practices (1 = Never to 5 = Always). These scales allow respondents to indicate the direction and degree of their beliefs as well as the frequency of their instructional practices related to chunk-based teaching and learning. To analyze the ordinal data, descriptive statistics for ranked

responses were used: the median (Mdn) for central tendency and the interquartile range (IQR) for dispersion and consensus.

Qualitative analysis provided additional insight into the quantitative findings by showing how English teachers perceived and implemented collocation-focused instruction in practice.

Results and discussion. Section A of the survey explored teachers' evaluation of chunk-based instruction across five statements regarding the role of collocations, fixed phrases, and formulaic expressions in ESL learning. Overall, the results indicate a clear and consistent tendency toward agreement with the principles of teaching language in chunks. This general tendency is statistically supported by a median score of 4 for all five statements, corresponding to the response category "agree." Furthermore, the interquartile range (IQR) values of 1–2 suggest relatively low variability in responses and a considerable degree of consensus among teachers.

Statement 1, concerning the effectiveness of teaching collocations and fixed phrases compared to teaching single words, received strong support from respondents, with **72%** of teachers selecting "agree" or "strongly agree." The median value of 4 indicates that the typical response fell within the agreement category, while the IQR of 2 reflects moderate dispersion, suggesting that although the majority supported this view, the intensity of agreement varied among respondents. These results demonstrate that teachers predominantly perceive multi-word units as pedagogically more effective than isolated lexical items. (See Table 1).

This result is consistent with previous research conducted by Khalil H. [16 p. 175-195] at Misr University for Science and Technology, which demonstrated that training learners in lexical chunks improves oral communication and supports a pedagogical shift from isolated word instruction to the systematic teaching of lexical chunks and their use in real communicative contexts.

Table 1.

Teachers' Evaluation of Chunk-Based Instruction in ESL Learning

Section A. Teachers' evaluation of chunk-based instruction	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Not sure	Agree	Strongly agree	Median	IQR
1. Teaching collocations and fixed phrases is more effective than teaching single words	5	13	10	39	33	4	2
2. Students learn to speak more naturally when they are taught language chunks.	4	18	9	40	29	4	2
3. Formulaic expressions play an important role in developing communicative competence.	2	8	10	36	44	4	1
4. Grammar is learned more effectively when presented through chunks.	9	11	18	34	28	4	2
5. Chunk-based teaching supports faster language production.	6	9	6	42	37	4	1

On the **second statement**, which addressed whether students learn to speak more naturally when they are taught language chunks, positive responses accounted for 69% of the total. The median of 4 again confirms overall agreement, and the IQR of 2 indicates moderate variability. This distribution shows that teachers largely associate chunk-based instruction with increased naturalness of learner speech, a core component of oral fluency.

These findings align with Mendoza [17], who reports that lexical chunks support more natural and fluent speech, enhance learner confidence, and that structured chunk instruction produces measurable improvements in oral fluency.

Statement 3, focusing on the role of formulaic expressions in developing communicative competence, produced the strongest consensus. The median value of 4, together with a narrow IQR of 1, indicates a high concentration of responses around agreement (80%). This finding suggests that teachers clearly recognize formulaic language as a central element in the development of communicative competence, rather than as a peripheral or supplementary component of language instruction.

With regard to **Statement 4**, which examined whether grammar is learned more effectively when presented through chunks, 62% of respondents expressed positive agreement. Although the median remained at 4, this item displayed the widest dispersion (IQR = 2) and the highest proportion of neutral responses. This pattern suggests that, while most teachers support grammar instruction through chunks, this aspect of chunk-based pedagogy is perceived as more complex and may be influenced by differences in methodological background or classroom practice.

This focus is supported by Asadova B. [18 p. 9-19], who argues that systematic instruction of collocations reinforces grammatical knowledge, deepens learners' understanding of contextual and cultural meaning, and enriches spoken language, leading to higher speaking quality.

Finally, **Statement 5**, addressing whether chunk-based teaching supports faster language production, received strong endorsement, with 79% of respondents selecting "agree" or "strongly agree." The median score of 4 combined with a low IQR of 1 indicates not only general agreement but also a high level of consistency in responses. This result highlights teachers' shared perception that chunk-based instruction facilitates automaticity and speed of language production, both of which are key indicators of fluency.

These findings suggest that teachers largely view collocations, fixed phrases, and formulaic expressions as effective instructional tools that support natural speech, communicative competence, grammatical development, and faster language production, thereby reinforcing the relevance of chunk-based instruction as a fluency-oriented pedagogical approach.

Section B of the survey examined how frequently teachers apply chunk-based techniques in classroom practice using a five-point Likert frequency scale (1 - never, to 5 - always). The responses to **statement 6** regarding the frequency of teaching collocations

and fixed expressions show that most teachers do so frequently, as reflected by a median score of 4 and an interquartile range of 2, although the extent of implementation varies. (See Table 2).

Table 2.

Teachers' Use of Chunk-Based Techniques in Classroom Practice

Section B. Classroom practice	Never	Seldom	Sometimes	Frequently	Always	Median	IQR
6. I teach collocations and fixed expressions in my lessons.	9	11	19	35	26	4	2
7. I include idioms or semi-fixed phrases in speaking activities.	4	16	28	30	22	4	1
8. I design tasks that encourage students to notice and use language chunks.	7	17	19	32	25	4	1,25
9. I correct students' errors by suggesting natural word combinations.	2	11	21	37	29	4	2
10. My teaching materials provide enough work on collocations and chunks.	9	11	22	34	24	4	1

For Statement 7, about the frequency of including idioms or semi-fixed phrases in speaking activities, the responses suggest that teachers regularly include idioms or semi-fixed phrases in speaking activities. A median score of 4 and IQR of 1 indicate consistent patterns, with 52% reporting “often” or “always” and 28% “sometimes.”

Statement 8 (“I design tasks that encourage students to notice and use language chunks”) reveals that 57% of teachers incorporate such tasks regularly (“often” 32%, “always” 25%). Another 19% selected “sometimes,” while 24% indicated rare use (“never” 7%, “seldom” 17%).

This lower frequency may be due to limited familiarity with the approach, time constraints, curriculum restrictions, or challenges in designing tasks suitable for students with varying proficiency levels.

With regard to **Statement 9** (“I correct students’ errors by suggesting natural word combinations”), this practice shows one of the highest frequencies: 66% of respondents chose “often” (37%) or “always” (29%), while 21% reported “sometimes.” Only 13% selected “never” (2%) or “seldom” (11%).

Finally, the responses to **statement 10** (“My teaching materials provide enough work on collocations and chunks”) show that teachers generally evaluate their instructional materials positively, with 58% selecting “agree” (34%) or “strongly agree” (24%). Meanwhile, 22% were uncertain (“not sure”), and 20% reported negative evaluations (“disagree” 11%, “strongly disagree” 9%). A median of 4 and an IQR of 1 indicate that typical responses fall within the “agree” category with relatively low dispersion, suggesting overall positive, though not uniform, perceptions of the materials’ support for chunk-based instruction.

The findings indicate that chunk-based instruction is a regular part of classroom practice for most teachers. The consistent central tendency and relatively low variability show that teachers generally apply chunk-focused techniques frequently, although some differences in implementation remain. Overall, the results suggest that chunk-based pedagogy is not merely theoretical but is actively and meaningfully integrated into everyday EFL teaching.

In Section C (statements 11-15), teachers’ responses were analyzed to assess perceived effects of chunk-based instruction on learners’ fluency.

Statement 11 (*Students who learn chunks speak more fluently*) yielded a median of 4 with an **IQR of 1**, reflecting strong agreement with relatively low dispersion. This indicates a high level of consensus among teachers regarding the fluency benefits of learning chunks. (See Table 3).

Previous experimental research conducted by Zafarghandi M. et al [19 p. 46-59] has demonstrated that explicit instruction in lexical chunks significantly improves

learners' speaking fluency, suggesting that chunk-based pedagogy represents a promising approach to fluency-oriented language teaching.

Monica's M. [20] study on undergraduate EFL learners demonstrated that chunking instruction facilitated improvements in speaking fluency, complementing the positive teacher attitudes toward chunk-based approaches observed in the present research.

Table 3.

Teachers' perceived effects of chunk-based instruction on speaking fluency

Section C. Perceived impact on fluency	Strongly disagree	disagree	not sure	agree	Strongly agree	Median	IQR
11. Students who learn chunks speak more fluently.	2	3	8	51	36	4	1
12. Chunk-based instruction reduces students' hesitation and long pauses.	4	6	7	44	39	4	1
13. Students recall and use vocabulary more easily when it is taught in chunks.	0	3	3	55	39	4	1
14. Teaching chunks improves students' confidence in speaking.	0	3	3	53	41	4	1
15. Chunk-based teaching improves both accuracy and fluency.	3	5	10	44	38	4	1

Statement 12 (*Chunk-based instruction reduces students' hesitation and long pauses*) also showed a median of 4 and an **IQR of 1**, suggesting that teachers largely agree that chunk instruction supports smoother speech production and reduces disfluency phenomena.

Statement 13 (*Students recall and use vocabulary more easily when it is taught in chunks*) demonstrated a median of 4 with an **IQR of 1**, pointing to a shared perception that chunk-based teaching enhances lexical retrieval and spontaneous use in speaking.

Statement 14 (*Teaching chunks improves students' confidence in speaking*) recorded a median of 4 and an **IQR of 1**, indicating a high degree of agreement and

minimal variability. This suggests that teachers widely associate chunk instruction with increased learner confidence during oral communication.

Statement 15 (*Chunk-based teaching improves both accuracy and fluency*) maintained a median of 4 with an **IQR of 1**, reflecting strong and consistent endorsement of the dual benefits of chunk-based instruction for both fluency and accuracy.

Teachers' responses in Section C reveal consistently positive and highly uniform perceptions of the impact of chunk-based instruction on learners' speaking fluency. All items recorded a median of 4 with a low IQR of 1, indicating strong agreement and high consensus. Teachers generally agreed that learning chunks improves students' fluency, reduces hesitation, supports easier vocabulary recall, increases speaking confidence, and enhances both fluency and accuracy. The low variability in responses suggests a shared belief among teachers that chunk-based instruction is an effective and reliable approach for developing spoken language skills.

The aim of section D of the survey (items 16–20) is to explore how teachers experience the practical implementation of chunk-based learning, including perceived difficulties and personal attitudes. (See Table 4).

Table 4.

Teachers' perceptions of challenges and attitudes toward chunk-based instruction

Section D. Challenges and attitudes	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Not sure	Agree	Strongly agree	Median	IQR
16. Teaching chunks requires more preparation than traditional vocabulary teaching.	5	8	20	39	28	4	2
17. Students find collocations difficult to master.	5	23	15	34	23	4	2
18. I need more training or resources on chunk-based instruction.	3	2	9	49	37	4	1

19. Chunk-based teaching should be an essential part of ESL methodology.	5	10	11	42	32	4	2
20. I plan to increase the use of chunk-based instruction in the future.	4	6	9	46	35	4	1

Statement 16 (Teaching chunks requires more preparation than traditional vocabulary teaching). A clear majority of respondents (67%) selected Agree or Strongly agree, suggesting that most teachers perceive chunk-based instruction as more time- and effort-intensive than traditional approaches. A less substantial group (33%) chose lower-scale options, which may reflect differences in teaching experience, access to ready-made materials, or familiarity with chunk-focused methodologies.

Statement 17 (Students find collocations difficult to master). With a median of 4 and an IQR of 2, responses again show overall agreement with moderate dispersion. The majority of teachers (57%) agreed or strongly agreed that collocations present difficulties for learners, confirming a widespread perception of collocations as a challenging area of vocabulary development. The considerable minority (43%) selecting lower categories may indicate variation in student proficiency levels, instructional techniques, or classroom exposure to collocational practice.

Statement 18 (I need more training or resources on chunk-based instruction). The item shows a median of 4 and a low IQR of 1, indicating strong and consistent agreement. A large majority of teachers (86%) agreed or strongly agreed, pointing to a clear need for further training and instructional resources.

Statement 19 (Chunk-based teaching should be an essential part of ESL methodology). With a median of 4 and an IQR of 2, responses reflect general agreement. A substantial majority (74%) supported integrating chunk-based instruction into ESL methodology, though some variation suggests differing methodological views.

Statement 20 (I plan to increase the use of chunk-based instruction in the future). This item also yielded a median of 4 and a low IQR of 1. A clear majority of respondents (81%) agreed, indicating strong intentions to expand the use of chunk-based teaching practices.

Taken together, the teachers' responses to the statements in this section reveals a dual perspective among teachers. While they clearly acknowledge the practical challenges of chunk-based instruction - particularly increased preparation demands and the difficulty students face in mastering collocations - they simultaneously express strong pedagogical commitment to this approach. The high levels of agreement regarding the need for further training, the methodological importance of chunk-based teaching, and intentions for future use indicate that teachers not only recognize its value but are also motivated to develop their professional competence in this area.

Conclusions. In conclusion, this study provides compelling evidence for the effectiveness of integrating chunk-based instruction, focusing on collocations and fixed expressions, into ESL curricula. Teachers recognize the value of this approach in enhancing fluency, confidence, and overall communicative competence in ESL learners. Despite the challenges associated with mastering collocations and the need for further training and resources, educators express a strong commitment to incorporating chunk-based teaching into their practice. These findings underscore the importance of systematic chunk instruction and pave the way for future research to explore its long-term effects on language production, as well as to develop practical recommendations for optimizing its implementation in ESL contexts.

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